

EMPOWERMENT THROUGH PARTICIPATION: POLITICAL ENGAGEMENT OF URBAN SLUM DWELLERS

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Abstract

This article explores the transformative potential of participatory political engagement among urban slum communities. This study investigates how involvement in political processes enables slum dwellers to assert their rights, influence policy decisions, and improve their living conditions. Through qualitative analysis of case studies and participatory action research, the paper examines the mechanisms through which political participation empowers marginalized communities, fostering social inclusion and civic agency. It delves into various forms of participation, including community organizing, advocacy campaigns, and grassroots initiatives, highlighting their role in challenging systemic inequalities and amplifying the voices of the marginalized. By shedding light on the experiences and strategies of urban slum dwellers, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of how participatory approaches can enhance democracy, promote social justice, and empower marginalized populations in urban settings.

Keywords: Empowerment, Participation, Urban slum dwellers, Political engagement, Social inclusion

1. Introduction:

The migration of rural populations to urban centers has been an enduring aspect of the global landscape, intimately linked with processes of globalization and economic advancement. This phenomenon has been driven by a multitude of factors, including but not limited to, the search for better economic opportunities, escape from rural poverty, and aspirations for a higher quality of life. As individuals and families migrate to urban areas in search of brighter prospects, they often encounter a harsh reality: the proliferation of informal settlements commonly referred to as urban slums. These urban slums, characterized by their haphazard construction, overcrowded living spaces, inadequate infrastructure, and lack of

basic services, represent a stark juxtaposition to the gleaming skyscrapers and bustling streets that define the modern urban landscape. For the millions who call these settlements home, life is a constant struggle against the backdrop of poverty, insecurity, and social marginalization (John Harriss Reviewed, 2007). Indeed, the challenges faced by residents of urban slums are manifold and deeply entrenched. Basic amenities such as clean water, sanitation facilities, and access to healthcare are often scarce, if not entirely absent. The absence of formal land tenure further exacerbates the vulnerability of slum dwellers, leaving them at the mercy of eviction threats and forced displacement. Moreover, the social fabric of slum communities is often frayed by pervasive crime, substance abuse, and other manifestations of social dislocation.

Amidst these adversities, one of the most pressing concerns facing slum residents is their political marginalization. Despite their significant numbers, slum dwellers are frequently excluded from mainstream political processes, their voices drowned out by more privileged segments of society. The lack of representation and advocacy translates into policies that overlook or neglect the needs of urban slum communities, perpetuating a cycle of poverty and disenfranchisement. It is within this context that the concept of political engagement emerges as a beacon of hope for urban slum dwellers. Participation in political processes offers a pathway to empowerment, enabling residents to assert their rights, advocate for their interests, and hold authorities accountable for their actions—or inactions. By actively engaging in the political sphere, slum dwellers seek to transcend their marginalized status and claim their rightful place as stakeholders in the urban landscape (Chattopadhyay, 2015). Crucially, political engagement encompasses a broad spectrum of activities, ranging from voting in elections to grassroots organizing and advocacy campaigns.

2. Understanding Urban Slum Dynamics

Before delving into the nuances of political engagement, it is essential to grasp the socio-economic context of urban slums. These settlements often emerge on the peripheries of cities, where land is cheap or illegally occupied. Lacking formal recognition and basic amenities, slum residents live in precarious conditions, grappling with poverty, insecurity, and social exclusion.

Understanding the dynamics of urban slums requires a comprehensive analysis of their socio-economic context, which encompasses various interrelated factors contributing to their formation, persistence, and challenges faced by their inhabitants. In this expanded discussion, we will explore the intricate web of conditions and circumstances that define

urban slums, shedding light on their origins, characteristics, and the diverse experiences of their residents.

2.1. Origins and Spatial Dynamics

Urban slums often emerge on the fringes of cities, where land is either cheaply available or illegally occupied. These settlements may arise spontaneously as a result of rapid urbanization, with migrants flocking to urban centers in search of livelihood opportunities. Informal land markets, characterized by informal transactions and lack of regulatory oversight, play a significant role in the proliferation of slum settlements. Additionally, historical factors such as colonial legacies and patterns of urban planning contribute to the spatial segregation of slum communities, perpetuating inequalities and exclusion.

Certainly, let's delve deeper into each of these sub-points to provide a more comprehensive understanding of their significance in shaping the dynamics of urban slums:

I.Role of Rapid Urbanization: Rapid urbanization, characterized by the unprecedented influx of rural migrants into cities, is a multifaceted phenomenon with profound implications for the growth and development of urban slums. Driven by a combination of economic aspirations and demographic pressures, this mass migration reflects the aspirations of individuals and families seeking better livelihood opportunities, improved access to education and healthcare, and escape from rural poverty and stagnation (Finch, 2023). The sheer scale and pace of rural-to-urban migration contribute to the exponential growth of urban populations, placing immense pressure on already strained urban infrastructure and services.

II.Informal Land Markets: The prevalence of informal land markets plays a pivotal role in facilitating the expansion of slum settlements, providing a fertile ground for the proliferation of informal housing and informal settlements. Unlike formal land markets governed by established legal frameworks and regulatory mechanisms, informal land transactions operate outside the purview of formal institutions, characterized by a lack of transparency, accountability, and legal protection for land rights. Informal land markets thrive in contexts where formal land tenure systems are inadequate or inaccessible to marginalized populations, such as rural migrants and low-income households.

III.Historical Context: The historical context of urban slum formation is shaped by a complex interplay of historical factors, including colonial legacies, discriminatory urban policies, and socio-political dynamics that have enduring implications for the spatial distribution of slum settlements and the socio-economic conditions of their inhabitants (Fox, 2008). Colonial legacies, rooted in centuries of colonial rule and exploitation, have left a profound imprint on

the spatial organization of cities in many regions of the world. Colonial urban planning and land policies often prioritized the interests of colonial powers and elite classes, leading to the segregation of urban space along racial, ethnic, and class lines.

2.2. Living Conditions and Infrastructure: Slum dwellers grapple with precarious living conditions characterized by overcrowded housing, inadequate sanitation facilities, and limited access to basic services such as clean water, electricity, and healthcare. The lack of formal infrastructure exacerbates vulnerabilities and exposes residents to health risks and environmental hazards. Moreover, informal construction methods and materials contribute to the vulnerability of slum settlements to natural disasters and urban hazards, further compounding the challenges faced by residents.

It is important to delve deeper into each of these sub-points to offer a more comprehensive insight into how they contribute to the complexities of challenges encountered by inhabitants of urban slums (Talukdar et al., 2010).

I. Overcrowded Housing: The phenomenon of overcrowded housing in urban slums is a consequence of the mismatch between housing demand and supply, exacerbated by rapid urbanization, limited land availability, and inadequate urban planning. Densely populated settlements with insufficient housing units force residents to live in cramped and congested conditions, often sharing small living spaces with multiple family members. The lack of adequate housing infrastructure leads to the proliferation of informal settlements characterized by makeshift dwellings, overcrowded tenements, and precarious housing structures.

II. Inadequate Sanitation: Inadequate sanitation facilities in urban slums pose significant health risks and environmental challenges for residents, undermining their well-being and perpetuating cycles of poverty and disease. The lack of proper sanitation infrastructure, including toilets, sewage systems, and solid waste management services, results in open defecation, indiscriminate waste disposal, and contamination of water sources, leading to the spread of waterborne diseases, diarrheal illnesses, and vector-borne infections (Sheuya, 2008). The consequences of inadequate sanitation extend beyond individual health outcomes to broader environmental and socio-economic impacts.

III. Limited Access to Basic Services: The limited access to basic services such as clean water, electricity, and healthcare exacerbates vulnerabilities and perpetuates cycles of poverty and deprivation in urban slums. Slum residents face formidable barriers in accessing essential services, including financial constraints, physical barriers, and institutional barriers, which

hinder their ability to meet their basic needs and realize their full potential. The consequences of limited access to basic services are profound, impacting residents' health outcomes, educational attainment, and economic opportunities.

IV. Vulnerability to Disasters: The vulnerability of urban slum settlements to natural disasters and urban hazards is a consequence of informal construction practices, precarious housing structures, and inadequate infrastructure, which amplify risks and exacerbate vulnerabilities for residents. Informal settlements are often located in hazard-prone areas, such as floodplains, riverbanks, and steep slopes, where land is cheap or illegally occupied, exposing residents to multiple hazards, including floods, landslides, fires, and earthquakes. The consequences of disasters in urban slums are devastating, resulting in loss of life, displacement, and destruction of homes and livelihoods (Alcayna, 2015).

2.3. Socio-Economic Characteristics: Slum populations exhibit diverse socio-economic profiles, reflecting the heterogeneity of migration patterns and livelihood strategies among residents. While some individuals may engage in informal employment in the informal sector, others may be unemployed or underemployed, facing barriers to accessing formal employment opportunities. Moreover, slum communities are often characterized by a lack of social cohesion and trust, stemming from diverse cultural backgrounds, linguistic differences, and socio-economic disparities among residents.

I. Informal Employment: A significant proportion of slum residents depend on informal sources of income for their livelihood, engaging in activities such as street vending, domestic work, and construction. These informal livelihoods often lack the stability of formal employment, exposing workers to precarious working conditions, low wages, and a lack of social protections. Without the security of regular employment contracts or access to benefits such as healthcare and pensions, slum dwellers face heightened economic insecurity and vulnerability.

II. Underemployment and Unemployment: Limited access to formal employment opportunities perpetuates high levels of underemployment and unemployment among slum dwellers, trapping them in a cycle of poverty and economic insecurity. The mismatch between the skills and qualifications of slum residents and the demands of formal job markets leaves many individuals underutilized and marginalized, unable to secure stable and dignified employment. As a result, slum residents often resort to informal sources of income, such as street vending, domestic work, or day labor, which offer little in the way of job security or social protections.

III.Social Fragmentation: The diverse migration patterns and socio-economic disparities present within slum communities contribute to social fragmentation and a lack of cohesion, undermining collective action and solidarity. The heterogeneity of slum populations, comprising individuals from diverse cultural, linguistic, and socio-economic backgrounds, creates barriers to social integration and cohesion, as residents struggle to find common ground and build trust across social divides. Moreover, entrenched inequalities and power imbalances perpetuate divisions within slum communities, exacerbating tensions and inhibiting collaboration towards common goals (Jimmy et al., 2020).

2.4. **Political Marginalization and Exclusion:** Slum dwellers confront systemic barriers to political participation and representation, stemming from historical neglect, discriminatory policies, and socio-economic disparities. Limited access to education, information, and resources further exacerbates their marginalization, rendering them voiceless in decision-making processes. Moreover, the stigmatization of slum residents perpetuates negative stereotypes and stereotypes, reinforcing patterns of exclusion and discrimination in political spheres (Koonings & Kruijt, 2009).

I.Structural Barriers: Systemic inequalities, rooted in historical injustices and perpetuated by socio-economic disparities, impose significant constraints on the ability of slum residents to engage meaningfully in formal political processes. Limited access to education perpetuates intergenerational cycles of poverty and disenfranchisement, as many slum dwellers lack the knowledge and skills necessary to navigate complex political systems and advocate for their rights. Furthermore, information asymmetry and digital divides exacerbate inequalities, as marginalized communities struggle to access reliable information and participate in public discourse.

II.Stigmatization and Discrimination: Negative stereotypes and prejudices against slum dwellers perpetuate social stigma and discrimination, further marginalizing these communities and excluding them from mainstream political discourse and decision-making processes. The pervasive narrative of slums as breeding grounds for crime, poverty, and social decay perpetuates misconceptions and biases that dehumanize and marginalize slum residents, denying them agency and dignity. Discriminatory attitudes and practices, fueled by deep-seated prejudices and entrenched power dynamics, create barriers to inclusion and participation, as slum dwellers face systemic barriers in accessing political representation and voicing their concerns.

III.Lack of Representation: Slum communities are often marginalized and underrepresented in formal political institutions, further exacerbating their political exclusion and disenfranchisement. The absence of proportional representation and electoral systems that prioritize marginalized voices perpetuates unequal power dynamics and reinforces the dominance of political elites and vested interests. Moreover, structural barriers such as voter suppression, gerrymandering, and restrictive electoral laws undermine the electoral participation of slum residents, denying them the opportunity to elect representatives who truly reflect their interests and concerns (Mahabir et al., 2016).

2.5. **Cultural Diversity and Social Dynamics:** Slum populations are characterized by cultural diversity and social complexity, reflecting the convergence of migrants from diverse backgrounds and regions. This diversity enriches the social fabric of slum communities, fostering resilience and adaptability in the face of adversity. However, it also poses challenges in terms of social cohesion, identity formation, and collective action, as residents navigate linguistic, cultural, and socio-economic differences in their daily lives (Mohapatra, 2013).

I.Cultural Diversity: Within the confines of slum settlements, a rich tapestry of cultural diversity unfolds, as these areas serve as convergence points for migrants hailing from diverse linguistic, ethnic, and religious backgrounds. The vibrant mosaic of cultures, traditions, and beliefs intermingles within the narrow alleys and makeshift dwellings, creating a kaleidoscope of identities and experiences. Each resident brings with them a unique heritage and worldview, enriching the social fabric of the community and contributing to its dynamic tapestry of diversity.

II.Social Cohesion and Adaptability: Despite the socio-economic disparities that pervade slum communities, a remarkable sense of resilience and solidarity often emerges, binding residents together in a collective bond forged through shared experiences and collective struggles. In the face of adversity, slum dwellers demonstrate remarkable resilience and resourcefulness, drawing strength from their communal ties and collective actions. Solidarity networks and mutual support mechanisms flourish within the community, as residents come together to confront common challenges and overcome shared obstacles.

III.Challenges of Diversity: However, the rich tapestry of cultural diversity within slum communities also presents a myriad of challenges, as residents grapple with the complexities of navigating cultural differences and socio-economic disparities in their daily lives. Cultural and linguistic barriers may hinder effective communication and social interaction,

exacerbating social divisions and inhibiting the formation of cohesive community bonds. Moreover, entrenched socio-economic disparities and power imbalances may exacerbate tensions and conflicts within the community, as residents vie for limited resources and opportunities.

Understanding the dynamics of urban slums requires a holistic perspective that encompasses the spatial, socio-economic, political, and cultural dimensions of these marginalized settlements.

3. **Challenges to Political Engagement In Urban Slums:** Despite their significant presence within urban landscapes, residents of slum settlements face a multitude of obstacles that impede their ability to engage meaningfully in political processes. These challenges stem from deep-rooted structural inequalities, entrenched power dynamics, and pervasive social stigmatization, which collectively undermine the political agency and representation of slum communities. Understanding and addressing these barriers is crucial for advancing inclusive governance and promoting the rights and interests of urban slum residents (Chattopadhyay, 2015).

3.1. **Structural Inequalities:** Rooted deeply in historical injustices and perpetuated by ongoing socio-economic disparities, structural inequalities present formidable barriers to political engagement for residents of urban slums. These systemic disparities undermine the ability of slum dwellers to navigate the intricacies of political systems and effectively advocate for their rights. Central to these challenges is the pervasive lack of access to education, information, and resources, which severely limits the capacity of slum residents to engage meaningfully in formal political institutions and processes. A glaring aspect of structural inequality is the stark educational divide prevalent in slum communities. Many residents lack formal education and literacy skills, a consequence of historical neglect and systemic barriers to quality education (Subadevan & Naqvi, 2017).

3.2. **Entrenched Power Dynamics:** Embedded within urban governance structures, entrenched power dynamics and patronage networks wield significant influence, often at the expense of marginalized slum communities. Within this framework, political elites and vested interests hold sway over decision-making processes, shaping policy agendas and resource allocation in manners that perpetuate existing inequalities and silence the voices of those dwelling in slum settlements. The resulting marginalization relegates slum residents to the periphery of political discourse, leaving them with scant avenues for meaningful

participation and representation. At the heart of these power dynamics lies the disproportionate influence wielded by political elites and entrenched interests.

3.3. **Social Stigmatization:** The insidious phenomenon of social stigmatization casts a long shadow over the lives of slum dwellers, perpetuating negative stereotypes and prejudices that undermine their agency, credibility, and political influence. Across mainstream media and public discourse, slum settlements are often portrayed as breeding grounds for crime, poverty, and social decay, painting a bleak and distorted picture of these communities. These portrayals not only reinforce misconceptions and biases but also dehumanize and marginalize residents, eroding their sense of dignity and belonging. At the heart of social stigmatization lies a web of discriminatory attitudes and practices, fueled by deep-seated prejudices and entrenched power dynamics.

4. **Strategies for Empowerment:** In the face of formidable challenges, urban slum dwellers have demonstrated remarkable resilience and resourcefulness, employing a variety of strategies to assert their political agency and advocate for their rights (Mehrohasani et al., 2021). These strategies, ranging from grassroots organizing to the use of technology, play a crucial role in mobilizing residents, raising awareness about their needs, and demanding recognition from policymakers. By harnessing these approaches, slum communities can challenge the status quo and push for meaningful change in their communities.

4.1. **Grassroots Organizations and Community-Based Movements:** In the complex landscape of urban slums, grassroots organizations and community-based movements emerge as beacons of hope, rallying residents together to confront the myriad challenges they face and advocate for their rights. These organizations, often spearheaded by local residents who intimately understand the struggles and aspirations of their communities, serve as catalysts for change, mobilizing collective action and fostering solidarity among slum dwellers. At the heart of grassroots organizing lies a deep commitment to amplifying the voices of marginalized urban residents (Cornwall & Guijt, 2004). By providing a platform for community members to come together and articulate their shared concerns, grassroots organizations empower slum dwellers to reclaim their agency and demand recognition from policymakers.

4.2. **Advocacy and Awareness-Raising Campaigns:** In the ongoing struggle for social justice and equality, advocacy and awareness-raising campaigns emerge as powerful tools for shedding light on the challenges faced by urban slum dwellers and mobilizing support for their rights. These campaigns serve as vehicles for amplifying the voices of marginalized

communities, shining a spotlight on pressing issues such as inadequate housing, lack of access to basic services, and systemic discrimination. Central to advocacy and awareness-raising campaigns is the use of various strategies to reach diverse audiences and spark meaningful dialogue.

4.3. Technology and Digital Mobilization: In the rapidly evolving landscape of urban activism, technology has emerged as a potent force for political mobilization and advocacy among urban slum dwellers. The proliferation of mobile phones and the ubiquity of social media platforms have transformed the way slum communities organize, communicate, and advocate for their rights. These technological tools provide a dynamic platform for residents to connect, share information, and mobilize collective action, amplifying their voices and fostering solidarity on a global scale. Social media platforms, such as Facebook, Twitter, and WhatsApp, serve as virtual gathering spaces where slum residents can exchange ideas, coordinate activities, and mobilize support for their causes.

4.4. Capacity Building and Leadership Development: Within the intricate fabric of urban slum communities, capacity building and leadership development initiatives emerge as indispensable pillars for fostering empowerment and driving transformative change. These initiatives are instrumental in equipping slum residents with the knowledge, skills, and resources necessary to navigate complex political systems, engage with formal institutions, and spearhead grassroots movements aimed at addressing their collective needs and aspirations. At the core of capacity building efforts lies a commitment to empowering slum dwellers to take charge of their own destinies and advocate for their rights effectively (Ho et al., 2023).

4.5. Coalition Building and Solidarity: In the intricate tapestry of urban advocacy, coalition building and solidarity efforts stand as pillars of strength, uniting urban slum dwellers with like-minded organizations and allies to amplify their voices and advocate for their rights. These efforts are pivotal for fostering collective action, leveraging collective strength, and effecting transformative change in the face of systemic injustices and inequalities. At the heart of coalition building lies the recognition of the power of unity in diversity. By forming coalitions with organizations and allies that share similar values and objectives, slum communities can pool their resources, expertise, and influence to advocate for policy change and hold decision-makers accountable.

5. Implications for Governance and Social Justice: The political engagement of urban slum dwellers represents a pivotal juncture in the trajectory of governance and social justice,

with profound implications for the fabric of society as a whole (Leshinsky et al., 2020). By embracing the voices and perspectives of marginalized communities in decision-making processes, policymakers can gain invaluable insights into the lived realities, needs, and aspirations of slum residents, thus paving the way for more inclusive and responsive governance. However, the significance of this engagement transcends mere policy formulation; it extends to the very foundations of social cohesion, community resilience, and equitable development.

First and foremost, the inclusion of marginalized voices in governance processes represents a fundamental tenet of democratic governance. By affording urban slum dwellers a seat at the table, policymakers acknowledge their agency as citizens and recognize their inherent right to participate in shaping the policies that affect their lives. This inclusivity not only enhances the legitimacy of governance structures but also fosters a sense of ownership and belonging among slum residents, empowering them to actively contribute to the collective well-being of their communities (Subbaraman et al., 2012).

6. **Conclusion:** In summation, the significance of political engagement among urban slum dwellers cannot be overstated in the discourse of urban governance. It represents a critical yet often overlooked facet of inclusive policymaking and democratic participation. By actively involving slum residents in political processes, we unlock their latent potential as agents of change and catalysts for societal progress. However, the realization of this potential demands concerted and sustained efforts to dismantle entrenched barriers, promote civic education, and cultivate inclusive institutions that prioritize the voices and needs of marginalized communities (Bhatia & Singh, 2019). At its core, empowering urban slum dwellers through political participation is not merely a moral imperative but a pragmatic necessity for building resilient, equitable, and vibrant cities. By harnessing the collective wisdom, resilience, and resourcefulness of slum communities, policymakers can unlock innovative solutions to complex urban challenges and foster inclusive development that leaves no one behind. Moreover, by amplifying the voices of slum residents in decision-making processes, we foster a sense of ownership and belonging that strengthens social cohesion and community resilience.

Yet, achieving meaningful political engagement among urban slum dwellers requires a multifaceted approach that addresses the root causes of marginalization and exclusion. This entails dismantling systemic barriers such as discrimination, lack of access to education and resources, and exclusionary governance structures that perpetuate cycles of poverty and

inequality. Moreover, it necessitates investment in civic education programs that empower slum residents with the knowledge, skills, and confidence to navigate political systems and advocate for their rights effectively (Nayak, 2019). Furthermore, fostering inclusive institutions that prioritize the participation and representation of slum communities is essential for building trust, legitimacy, and accountability in governance processes. By ensuring that slum residents have a seat at the table and a stake in decision-making, we foster a more responsive and equitable urban governance system that reflects the diversity and complexity of urban realities. Moreover, inclusive institutions provide the necessary infrastructure and support for slum communities to organize, mobilize, and articulate their demands in ways that resonate with policymakers and drive meaningful change.

Reference:

- Alcayna, T. (2015). *Slum Socio-Ecology: An exploratory characterisation of vulnerability to climate-change related disasters in the urban context*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.2294.2800>
- Bhatia, S., & Singh, S. (2019). Empowering Women Through Financial Inclusion: A Study of Urban Slum. *Vikalpa*, 44(4), 182–197. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0256090919897809>
- Chattopadhyay, S. (2015). Contesting inclusiveness: Policies, politics and processes of participatory urban governance in Indian cities. *Progress in Development Studies*, 15, 22–36. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1464993414546969>
- Cornwall, A., & Guijt, I. M. (2004). Shifting perceptions, Changing Practices in PRA: From Infinite Innovation to the Quest for Quality. *PLA Notes (2004)* 50, 50.
- Finch, J. (2023). The Origin of Slum as a Trans-Class Concept. *Journal of Urban History*, 49(3), 492–504. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00961442221127054>
- Fox, S. (2008). *On the Origins and Consequences of Slums*.
- Ho, S., Choudhury, P. R., & Joshi, R. (2023). Community participation for inclusive land administration: A case study of the Odisha urban slum formalization project. *Land Use Policy*, 125, 106457. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.106457>
- Jimmy, E. N., Martinez, J., & Verplanke, J. (2020). Spatial Patterns of Residential Fragmentation and Quality of Life in Nairobi City, Kenya. *Applied Research in Quality of Life*, 15(5), 1493–1517. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11482-019-09739-8>

- John Harriss Reviewed. (2007). Antinomies of Empowerment: Observations on Civil Society, Politics and Urban Governance in India. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 42(26), 2716–2724.
- Koonings, K., & Kruijt, D. (2009). *Megacities: The Politics of Urban Exclusion and Violence in the Global South*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Leshinsky, R., Ho, S., & Choudhury, P. (2020). Social Innovation as a Disruptor of Tenure: Recognising Land Rights of Slum Dwellers in Odisha, India. In A. Lehari & R. Levine-Schnur (Eds.), *Disruptive Technology, Legal Innovation, and the Future of Real Estate* (pp. 81–99). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-52387-9_5
- Mahabir, R., Crooks, A., Croitoru, A., & Agouris, P. (2016). The study of slums as social and physical constructs: Challenges and emerging research opportunities. *Regional Studies, Regional Science*, 3(1), 399–419. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21681376.2016.1229130>
- Mehrolhasani, M. H., Yazdi-Feyzabadi, V., & Ghasemi, S. (2021). Community empowerment for health promotion in slums areas: A narrative review with emphasis on challenges and interventions. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, 10, 263. https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_1628_20
- Mohapatra, T. (2013). Tribes of Odisha: Issues of social inclusion, exclusion and cultural assimilation. *Bodhi: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, 5(1), 16–33. <https://doi.org/10.3126/bodhi.v5i1.8043>
- Nayak, B. C. (2019). *Political Empowerment and Inclusive Development of Tribals through PRIs- A Study in Gajapati District of Odisha*.
- Sheuya, S. A. (2008). Improving the Health and Lives of People Living in Slums. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1136(1), 298–306. <https://doi.org/10.1196/annals.1425.003>
- Subadevan, & Naqvi, I. (2017). Contesting urban citizenship: The urban poor's strategies of state engagement in Chennai, India. *International Development Planning Review*, 39(1), 77–95. <https://doi.org/10.3828/idpr.2017.5>
- Subbaraman, R., O'brien, J., Shitole, T., Shitole, S., Sawant, K., Bloom, D. E., & Patil-Deshmukh, A. (2012). Off the map: The health and social implications of being a non-notified slum in India. *Environment and Urbanization*, 24(2), 643–663. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956247812456356>

Talukdar, D., Jack, D., & Gulyani, S. (2010). *Poverty, Living Conditions, And Infrastructure Access: A Comparison Of Slums In Dakar, Johannesburg, And Nairobi*. The World Bank. <https://doi.org/10.1596/1813-9450-5388>